

FEATURES OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF VETERINARY STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the analysis of the formation of professional competence in the process of teaching English, the author examines the structure of professional competence for veterinary students, examines the difficulty of developing interpersonal competencies among students of non-linguistic universities.*

Keywords: *professional competence, interpersonal competence, general cultural competence, communication skills, ethics of veterinary activity, search for innovations, Internet resources, modern educational technologies, motivation.*

The study of foreign languages in modern society is becoming an inseparable component of the professional training of specialists of various profiles and the quality of their language training largely depends on the successful solution of issues of professional growth.

The increasing role of the English language in the formation of key and professional competencies of veterinary students is conditioned by the expansion of international interuniversity relations.

The educational standards of recent years reflect the replacement of the main paradigm: the emphasis has shifted from the knowledge paradigm to the competence one; the task is to purposefully form general cultural and professional competencies by strengthening interdisciplinary connections and approaches to the learning process, using modern information technologies, modeling professional communication situations, etc.

For disciplines related to foreign languages, the task is complicated by the need to form not only language skills and abilities, but also actively contribute to the development of professional skills, not only communication skills, but professional communication skills. In this regard, the problem of effective ways of forming professional competencies among university students is largely updated.

In modern society, a successful graduate must have a certain level of professional competence. Professional competence consists of the business and personal qualities of a specialist, his knowledge, skills, experience necessary for the successful implementation of professional activity, the ability to analyze and predict the results of work [1, p. 136]. Professional competence for any profession consists of a certain set of universal and professional competencies. Effective implementation of practical veterinary activities involves the possession of the following competencies:

- 1) the breadth and depth of knowledge and their meaningful application, taking into account the specifics of a particular situation;
- 2) analysis of veterinary problems;
- 3) development and adoption of pedagogical decisions;

- 4) evaluation of veterinary activities;
- 5) social responsibility;
- 6) compliance with legislation and legal norms;
- 7) ethics of veterinary activity;
- 8) organization and management of veterinary activities;
- 9) communication skills;
- 10) lifelong learning;
- 11) responsibility for decisions in the field of professional activity;
- 12) search and implementation of innovations.

According to a survey of students in the direction of "Veterinary Medicine" of the Tashkent branch of the Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology, the most significant competence is the ability to solve veterinary problems (52%). 60% of respondents consider it important to develop and make pedagogical decisions in the field of veterinary activities. Competent organization and management of veterinary activities and in-depth knowledge are important for half of the students. 43% of respondents are ready to be responsible for veterinary decisions, social responsibility and comply with legislation. The ability to evaluate veterinary activities is considered important by 39% of respondents, communication skills – 62%. Only 33% of respondents realize the importance of lifelong learning. The most "unpopular" competencies (28%) were the search and implementation of innovations, as well as the ethics of veterinary activities.

The main part of the listed competencies is formed in the process of studying specialized disciplines. However, their formation would be incomplete without studying general education disciplines. When asked about the disciplines that help develop the above competencies, the students listed the following general education disciplines along with the profile ones: philosophy, pedagogy and psychology, law, native language and speech culture, foreign language.

No successful professional activity is impossible without the possession of communication skills. By communication skills we mean readiness for effective oral and written communication in the course of their professional activities, including in a foreign language. The majority of respondents (72%) do not understand the definition of "communication skills". However, 83% of respondents agree that studying the discipline "Foreign language" is an effective tool for improving the level of communication skills.

We believe that the professional orientation of teaching a foreign language allows you to develop not only communication skills, but also helps in the development of many other competencies. Students acquire knowledge that they will need in their future activities, experience overcoming obstacles and achieving important goals, learn to solve professional problems and not only to make effective decisions.

To achieve this goal, foreign language teachers need to use various teaching tools, technologies and methods, making them personally significant and professionally oriented. Internet resources, multimedia software tools as modern pedagogical technologies of teaching and upbringing, active and interactive methods are used to achieve these goals. A

The trend of the XXI century is considered to be smart education, which uses all the content available online. Internet resources, where not only textual material is presented, but also there are many opportunities for enriching vocabulary and modeling real situations of professional communication, have become the most accessible source of professionally significant authentic

material. Their methodically developed use significantly increases the effectiveness of the educational process, forms socially significant qualities for professional activity.

The professional orientation of foreign language teaching makes it possible to fully and harmoniously develop the competencies of students that are important for personal and professional success. In the process of learning a foreign language, students are taught the following skills: 1) analyze, summarize and find information; 2) work individually, with a partner and in a team; 3) evaluate and criticize; 4) perceive diversity and cross-cultural differences; 5) show tolerance; 6) choose the appropriate behavior model for the situation. For students of non-linguistic universities, the greatest difficulty is the development of interpersonal competencies, which are a prerequisite for successful professional activity. It is necessary to teach students to express feelings and attitudes, to think critically, to be tolerant, as well as to work in groups, to make social and ethical commitments.

It is more expedient to use different types of textbooks and teaching aids, conceptually combine them, be sure to connect listening, visualize the teaching material; this helps students not only develop receptive skills of perception of foreign language speech, but also observe the style of behavior of native speakers corresponding to the communication situation. Studying topics such as "Youth Problems", writing comments to articles on various social and cultural issues forms the most important moral qualities, such as empathy, tolerance, respect for elders, as well as communication skills (constructive communication, the ability to understand other people's problems and help solve them).

The main technique of professionally oriented foreign language teaching is interesting, modern and relevant texts in the specialty. Not every university has modern textbooks with such texts available. In addition, they become obsolete very quickly and lose their relevance. Therefore, it is important for a foreign language teacher to select the material that will interest the student. The use of a pre- and post-text set of tasks and exercises allows students to master the basic vocabulary of the specialty and learn how to extract key information. The student should also learn how to use the information read in speech (monologue, dialogue). Such teaching methods are most appropriate to use in the second year of study (3rd, 4th semester), after students have mastered the basic basic grammatical material and conversational topics in the first year of study.

The choice of professionally-oriented tasks depends, first of all, on the position of the student. Depending on the activity of students in foreign language classes, the following technologies can be used: problem discussions, project method, case technologies, brainstorming, game technologies (business and role-playing games, dramatization, etc.), reading and writing as a means of developing critical thinking, etc.

Increasing interest in learning a foreign language and awareness of its connection with the future profession can be achieved not only by traditional methods and means, but also through creative tasks (for example, participation in a festival of videos promoting the need to learn a foreign language for a future profession); through students' participation in conferences, round tables, discussion clubs with native speakers. In addition, an effective contribution to the study of a foreign language could be the writing of part of course and diploma projects in a foreign language and the mandatory use of up-to-date authentic sources. Teaching special subjects in a foreign language is also an effective tool of a professionally oriented approach.

The following aspects can be attributed to the elements of a successful lesson that develops the competencies necessary for professional activity:

- student orientation: the subject and methodology of the lesson should be focused on students and take into account their previous knowledge;
- problem orientation: students should be able to formulate a problem on their own and solve it with the help of knowledge gained in the classroom;
- self-organization: the student should be able to independently organize part of the lesson;
- example-based learning: specific examples should serve to develop each competence;
- focus on comprehension: it is necessary to have a meaningful perception of the educational process by students. Unlike bachelors, students at the second stage of higher education (master's degree) rank preferences of professional competencies differently.

They better understand that the requirements for a specialist have changed qualitatively, that today several forms of activity in production closely interact – design and research activities are added to the production. That production, which is not aimed at developing more efficient technologies, is doomed to lose in the competition in the free market.

Therefore, such competence as the search and implementation of innovations ranks high among them according to the results of surveys. That is why the problem of transformation of the educational process at the university is being solved. Education should become "activity-based", and not just "knowledge-based", and, accordingly, the educational and cognitive activities of students should be modified into research and design. Disciplines related to a foreign language can contribute to this to a large extent, since they can "draw" experience in mastering new technologies with the help of a foreign language. A huge number of scientific and technical materials that have not been introduced into scientific circulation in Uzbekistan are available to them, and they can use it, strengthening their motivational field. They are more aware of the importance of lifelong learning, observing how quickly their knowledge becomes obsolete (the field of engineering is one of the most rapidly updated areas in terms of technology).

Undergraduates are characterized by stronger and formed motivation, already possess sufficient professional horizons. Many already have work experience in manufacturing or in business, or in education. This audience is efficient, has good skills of independent work, analysis of a large amount of information of various kinds, including professional, is able and willing to learn. Communication is not difficult in most cases; they are more determined to communicate in a foreign language.

One of the important competencies of a future master's degree is the ability to work with narrowly focused professional literature, sources in a foreign language in order to gather a research base for his master's thesis. Active search for materials on the topic of scientific research and work with English-language sites are aimed at expanding the professional vocabulary. The scientific component is one of the most important in the content of the training course, and in this regard, equal attention is paid not only to the development of vocabulary skills, the selection of grammatical means, terminology, reading, analysis and semantic compression of the content of voluminous professional materials, speech, etiquette skills, but also the skills of "academic writing", annotation, abstracting texts by specialty.

This includes the formation of such skills as setting a goal and correctly formulating research tasks in a foreign language, drawing up a plan of scientific work, reviewing sources on your scientific topic. Describe and accurately translate the information presented in graphical and tabular forms, take notes, analyze the results of the study. To compose a letter with a proposal for cooperation, a grant application, an advertising and recommendation letter, write an essay, a

scientific article, etc. A whole range of various skills and abilities is being developed in order to form professional skills for undergraduates.

For both bachelors and undergraduates, a foreign language will be not only a subject of study, but also a means of learning. A special role in the formation of professional competence is played by contextual learning technology (learning in the context of students' future profession). With the help of a foreign language, it is also possible to successfully model the subject content of professional activity (situations, fragments), as well as with the help of basic subjects.

Game design (quasi-professional activity), cases that allow you to involve in solving specific problems, business games, etc. A wide variety of effective learning technologies are used abroad today. Experts agree that in the electronic age, it is necessary to tightly involve the entire physical and virtual environment in order to solve the problem of competence-based learning in higher education.

In the works of specialists and practitioners, innovators in the field of higher education, the real experience of transforming the space for learning and teaching is described, covering a wide range of factors (physical, virtual, formal, informal, mixed, flexible, etc.). Innovative practices, strategies, and initiatives for competence-based education are presented in many works. But this is more of a task for foreign language teachers who need to develop or change their methodological thinking, master the most modern pedagogical technologies in order to use them in the process of teaching students.

Thus, professional competence consists of a set of competencies, the formation of which occurs with the help of various disciplines of the curriculum. Teaching a foreign language is an integral part of the process of forming a competent university graduate. Successfully implemented professionally oriented foreign language teaching will allow graduates of the university to become competitive and worthy citizens of society in the future.

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